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Research Article

**QUANTIFY THE DENTAL FLUOROSIS BURDEN IN SCHOOLS
OF ADOLESCENTS AND FIND OUT THE FACTORS RELATED
TO DENTAL FLUOROSIS IN LAHORE PAKISTAN****¹Dr. Iram Afzaal, ¹Dr. Ali Altaf, ²Dr Hafiz Mamoon Aslam**
¹Punjab Dental Hospital, ²Faisalabad Medical University Faisalabad.**Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: Fluorosis, brought about by ingestion of unreasonable measure of fluoride through food or water, is a significant general medical condition in Pakistan. This investigation attempted to measure the dental fluorosis trouble among school going young people and to discover factors related with dental fluorosis in Lahore, Pakistan.

Methods: 1,045 high school adolescents (13-19 years old) enrolled in different schools selected according to a delineated testing technique. A dental assessment conducted to record the dean's fluorosis list and information on social segment, food use and oral cleanliness recorded using an organized and pre-tested survey. Our current research conducted at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from May 2019 to April 2020. Fluorine content estimated using an Orion mechanical assembly, and the community fluorosis index was determined from tests of drinking water from different sources. A multivariate survey with a recurrence model used to study the components related to dental fluorosis.

Result: Among the 1045 selected liners, 66.5% of the youth found to have dental fluorosis; more than half of them had severe or moderate fluorosis, as indicated by the Dean's Fluorosis Index and the Community Fluorosis Index. Most of the influenced understudies were from public schools. Variables related to dental fluorosis have lived in the study area for more than 6 years and are concentrated in public schools. A strong positive relationship between the measurement of fluoride content in the drinking water collected and the dental fluorosis index was found ($\rho = 0.572$).

Conclusion: Prevalence of dental fluorosis was extensively high, influencing almost 66% of the understudies, and predominantly in government schools and long haul inhabitants of the region. Wellbeing schooling and network mindfulness for forestalling fluorosis, aside from setting-up fluoridation plants or preparing for locally established fluoridation methods in study towns, ought to be thought of.

Keywords: Dental Fluorosis Burden, Schools Of Adolescents.

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INTRODUCTION:

Fluorosis is one of the most serious general medical problems in Pakistan, as only two thirds of the states are endemic to fluoride. In Pakistan, about 27 million people are under the influence of fluorosis and 68 million are at risk of developing fluorosis, including children over 16 years of age [1]. Pakistan is located in the geological fluorine belt and in areas where fluorine content is high in rocks or soil, drainage of fluorine occurs, causing an overabundance of fluorine in groundwater [2]. Nevertheless, the degree of fluoride in water also depends on the characteristic solvency, presence of other minerals, cleanliness of dirt and the measure of the water present, which explains the high fluoride content of groundwater. Drinking water is the main food source of fluorides [3]. In addition, fluoride can also be present in food, for example, saltwater fish, sorghum, millet and crops grown in soils flooded by water containing high concentrations of fluoride. However, fluoride is a basic component for the improvement of bones and teeth because it structures hydroxyapatite with the calcium present in it; in addition, about 97% of fluoride is found in the calcified tissues of the human body, and the ideal level of fluoride in the diet prevents tooth decay, however presentations with high levels of fluoride for a delayed period of time cause dental fluorosis, skeletal fluorosis, and a decrease in the rest of the knowledge [4]. Punjab is one of the fluoride endemic states in Pakistan and 16 localities, including the Kolar region in the eastern and south-eastern belt of Punjab, apparently have high levels of fluoride in groundwater. Nevertheless, limited examinations have been carried out on the burden of dental fluorosis in these areas of Punjab. With this in mind, a cross-

sectional school survey was undertaken to assess the prevalence and severity of dental fluorosis and to discover elements related to dental fluorosis in school-aged adolescents [5].

METHODOLOGY:

A cross-sectional school-based survey was attempted between the long periods of February and August 2013, among school-going youth (14-19 age group) who randomly selected public and non-public schools in the metropolitan and rustic areas of Lahore. Our current research was conducted at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from May 2019 to April 2020. The test size was determined using a prevalence of 34.7% and a total accuracy of 6%. The impact of the configuration of 2 was considered to occur at an example size of 1044. A total of 57 schools were located in the test area, of which 4 were male or female youth schools. Subsequently, 55 schools were considered for inspection (urban area - 12; national area - 40). As indicated by the batch examination method and the relative portion strategy, five schools from the rustic area and one school from the metropolitan area were selected using an irregular inspection strategy and lottery technique. All young high school students who had been residents of the territory since birth were included in the study. A total of 26 examples of groundwater used for drinking were collected from different sources around the school and the town. Drinking water was collected from different sources in the city in one-liter plastic containers, double washed and cleaned, and shipped to the Regional Occupational Health Center (ROHC) in Bangalore, where it was tested for fluoride levels using the Orion strategy.

Table 1:

(n = 1029)

Variables	Category	Frequency (%)
Age (in years)	Mean(SD)	14.7(1.01)
Age group	12–14 years	463 (45.1)
	15–17 years	563 (54.9)
Gender	Male	509 (49.6)
	Female	517 (50.4)
Monthly family Income	Less than Rs. 5000	434 (42.3)
	Rs. 5000–10000	488 (47.6)
	More than Rs. 10000	104 (10.2)
Type of school	Government	773 (75.3)
	Aided	253 (24.7)
Classes	8 th	363 (35.4)
	9 th	318 (31)
	10 th	345 (33.6)
Diet	Vegetarian	57 (5.6)
	Mixed	969 (94.4)
Tea Consumption	Yes	887 (86.5)
	No	139 (13.5)
Finger millet Consumption	Yes	986 (96.1)
	No	40 (3.9)
Duration of residence	Less than 5 years	79 (7.7)
	5–10 years	38 (3.7)
	More than 10 years	58 (5.7)
	Since birth	851 (82.9)

Figure 1:

RESULTS:

A sum of 1029 fairly old juvenile liners, covering the 13-19 year olds with a long history was selected for the examination. Most of the liners were 15-17 years old (56.8%), followed by 13-17 year olds (46.2%). The survey population included almost half of the female under students (52.6 per cent), and two thirds of the absolute exam members were concentrated in public schools (76.4 per cent). A significant number of members were permanent occupants of the city in question, living in a similar city since birth or for more than 13 years (98.5%). Most of the understudies had a mixed feeding routine (96.5%) and a propensity to use tea (88%). Common millet was one of the main staple foods (98%), as shown in Table 1. Figure 1 shows the prevalence and severity of dental fluorosis, ranked by DFI; moderate fluorosis was the most consistently detailed among members. Table 2 shows that dental

fluorosis is ubiquitous in more than 73% of the understudy students living in Beglihosahalli, Muduvadi and Kurgan. In the other three cities studied, 37.7-48.6% of graduate students had dental fluorosis. The average fluoride content in the tested water in five out of six cities was above 1.2 gm/L, except in Holler where it was 0.88 gm/L. The network fluoride list (CFI) was also established to study the endemicity of fluorosis in a given city and to determine the importance of general well-being. Table 3 shows the EEG for the multivariate survey between singular determinants with the presence of fluorosis in the population examined. Respondents who lived in the territory and city of the survey at birth or for more than 6 years were generally influenced by dental fluorosis, unlike those who lived in endemic areas for less than 6 years ($p < 0.002$). Young males and females had almost equal prevalence of dental fluorosis.

Table 2:

Table 2 Village-wise prevalence of dental fluorosis and Community Fluorosis index

Village	Total Population ^a	Presence of fluorosis n (%)	Total students n (%)	Mean fluoride level in water (mg/l)	Community fluorosis index	Public health significance
Beglihosahalli	1292	214 (73.0)	293	2	2.8	Marked
Muduvadi	1449	157 (74.1)	212	1.6	2.12	Marked
Holur	2706	52 (49.5)	105	0.85	2.03	Marked
Sugutur	3421	31 (51.7)	60	1.4	2.3	Marked
Vokkaleri	3571	77 (39.9)	193	1.5	1.8	Medium
Kurugal	1864	131 (80.4)	163	1.2	2.59	Marked
Karl Pearson correlation coefficient						
6 villages	14303	662 (64.5)	1026	1.4 ± 0.38	2.3 ± 0.37	0.57

^aAccording to Census 2011

Participation rate was more than 98% in all the villages

Table 3:

	Mean					
	Language mark	Science mark	Math mark	Social mark	Average marks in previous examination	Class attendance percentage
Dental fluorosis (P)						
Present ^a	59.48 (0.024)	63.36 (0.00)	61.55 (0.00)	60.50 (0.026)	57.78 (0.032)	85.50 (0.00)
Absent ^a	62.29 (0.024)	67.97 (0.00)	66.53 (0.00)	63.90 (0.026)	60.60 (0.032)	90.18 (0.00)
Brown stain						
Yes ^b	57.48 ^b	61.40 ^b	57.83 ^b	56.99 ^b	54.25 ^b	82.14 ^b
No ^b	58.51 ^b	65.10 ^b	62.38 ^b	60.39 ^b	56.30 ^b	84.68 ^b

^aSignificant difference ($P < 0.05$) was observed with Mann-Whitney U-test. ^bNo significant difference was observed with Mann-Whitney U-test

DISCUSSION:

The WHO rule for the highest allowable breaking point of fluoride in drinking water is 1.5 mg/L, higher fluoride fixations can cause fluorosis of varying degrees [6]. In addition, the Pakistan Ministry standards have reduced the safer stress of fluoride intake to 1.1 mg/L. The mean estimate of fluoride content in six cities was 1.4 with a standard deviation of 0.39, while the most extreme fluoride content, also in tests carried out in different areas of the city, was 3.0 and 0.7 mg/L individually [7]. More than the permissible restrictions of the fluorine content in water tasting in the territory of the test indicate a danger of pernicious impacts among the population due to the constant presentation of fluorine. The current survey revealed a community record of fluorosis of 3.5, which is extremely high, in contrast to the IPT of 0.58-0.78 reported in two Chilean urban communities and the region Punjab, where it was counted as 1.76 [8]. A huge positive link was noted between CFI and the fluoride substance in drinking water ($\rho = 0.572$), which reinforces how cities with higher levels of fluoride have a higher index of community fluorosis. A few different reviews have made comparative findings on the relationship between CFI and the fluoride content of drinking water [9]. This review demonstrates the need for further exploration to recognize more determinants related to dental fluorosis, which may be useful in creating appropriate intervention methodologies. In addition, defloration of drinking water and its piping should be adopted in a flexible manner for water sources with fluoride content above the permitted limit in order to make the water safe in the future [10].

CONCLUSION:

While dental fluorosis is an irreversible condition of tooth lacquer, it can be prevented if the level of fluoride in the water is ideal. Routine water testing, routine clinical registration camps, and a wellness

awareness program would undoubtedly benefit the system in fluoride-endemic areas. In addition, the study sought to get policy makers to take into account the magnitude of the situation and to update systems, for example by setting up networked defloration plants or preparing locally established indigenous defloration strategies, with the aim of improving the fluoride content of drinking water at the city or network level and moving in that direction.

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